

Intermediate report on the stakeholder engagement,
exploitation, dissemination, communication and
standardisation activities
D13.4

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About OneNet

OneNet will provide a seamless integration of all the actors in the electricity network across Europe to create the conditions for a synergistic operation that optimizes the overall energy system while creating an open and fair market structure.

The project OneNet (One Network for Europe) is funded through the EU's eighth Framework Programme Horizon 2020. It is titled "TSO – DSO Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" and responds to the call "Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future (LC)".

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to adapt to this changing environment and adjust their current business model to accommodate faster reactions and adaptive flexibility. This is an unprecedented challenge requiring an unprecedented solution. For this reason, the two major associations of grid operators in Europe, ENTSO-E and EDSO, have activated their members to put together a unique consortium.

OneNet sees the participation of a consortium of more than 70 partners. Key partners in the consortium include: ENTSO-E and EDSO, Elering, EDP Distribution, RWTH Aachen University, University of Comillas, VITO, European Dynamics, Ubitech, Engineering, and the EU's Florence School of Regulation (Energy).

The key elements of the project are:

1. Definition of a common market design for Europe: this means standardized products and key parameters for grid services which aim at the coordination of all actors, from grid operators to customers;
2. Definition of a Common IT Architecture and Common IT Interfaces: this means not trying to create a single IT platform for all the products, but enabling an open architecture of interactions among several platforms, so that anybody can join any market across Europe; and
3. Large-scale demonstrators to implement and showcase the scalable solutions developed throughout the project. These demonstrators are organized in four clusters coming to include countries in every region of Europe and testing innovative use cases never validated before.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ADB	Advisory and Dissemination Board
FSR	Florence School of Regulation
GA	General Assembly
PMT	Project Management Team
WP13	Work Package 13

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the main reference for stakeholder engagement, exploitation, dissemination, communication and standardisation activities of the Horizon2020 OneNet project. This deliverable serves as both an update on these activities for the EU, as well as the consortium itself, along with any other interested stakeholders. It summaries the state of play of the various activities covered and, where appropriate, provides insights on measures that are working well and suggestions where areas can be improved.

WP13 is responsible for dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities and, therefore, it is transversal to the rest of the work packages. For that reason, all work packages have contributed in different ways to the production of this deliverable.

This deliverable is organised as follows: Section 1 provides a brief introduction to this intermediate report as well as the followed methodology; Section 2 reviews the results achieved by the Dissemination and Communication Plan and related activities; and Section 3 analyses the stakeholders engagement. Finally, the deliverable is concluded with Section 4, summarising the most important achievements so far, which will serve as the basis for the future exploitation plan.

1 Introduction

The scope of the communication and dissemination activities of OneNet is three-fold:

- the development of a Communication and Dissemination Plan will help raise awareness on the project and possibly create synergies and new levels of cooperation among the players, customers and stakeholders for “One Network for Europe”;
- the dissemination activities (along with the interactive forum “GRIFOn”, which is coordinated by WP12) will create consensus and acceptance of the established solution externally and internally; and
- the solution has commercial value in the grid services market. In this respect, communication activities will help ensure products are more marketable.

Each of the main communication tasks take a different approach in order to complement each other. The three tasks are as follows:

Task 13.1 ‘Project identity and communication and dissemination strategy’ is the foundation to develop the project’s communication activities, composed of the main elements that are key for the project identity: corporate identity, document templates, informative project material, and website. The project website provides clear and engaging information about the project activities and events and gathers the project’s public findings. The website is constantly updated and benefits from a strong connection with the social media channels.

Task 13.2 ‘Dedicated communication activities’ covers the communication and outreach activities aimed at communicating to a more general audience. Specific actions are: creating and managing a new dedicated database; developing a project video; creating awareness of the project through social media (LinkedIn, Twitter); producing articles, interviews and webinars to be published on the project website; preparing newsletters to be distributed to the OneNet database; and supporting project partners in contributing to the project blog. The website also hosts a project blog, which will feature valuable insights from the sector, including contributions from project partners.

Task 13.3 ‘Fostering adoption of OneNet results’ will integrate the network and expertise of various stakeholders into revising and adapting the OneNet strategy and adoption. The Advisory and Dissemination Board (ADB) serves as an opportunity to identify changes in the framework, new challenges and opportunities. In addition, the ADB should advise with regards to the communication of results to stakeholders and help opening dissemination paths in preparation of further exploitation of OneNet results. With the support of the extensive networks of OneNet partners, this task will also rely on consultation with associations in the energy domain; Standards Development Organisations; and Policy and Governance representatives on the European, international as well as national levels.

Milestones:

- MS37: Project website with private area (M5);
- MS38: Databases of stakeholders created (M10): Gathering relevant contacts from all the partners involved, creating and managing a new dedicated database;
- MS39: Open days at three trial sites presenting and discussing prototype solutions (M20);
- MS40: Two exploitation workshops (M24): Two exploitation workshops will be organised during the development of the project to identify the options, to align partners view and to prepare the correspondent plans; and
- MS41: One final OneNet conference (M36): A final conference will gather experts in the sector to discuss the innovation proposed by OneNet.

1.1 Target Audience

The target audience has been identified based on a number of factors, including: analysis of audiences from previous projects implemented by the consortium, mapping of partners and stakeholders, and research of similar projects external to the consortium.

The key audience groups have been identified as follows:

- System Operators (TSOs, DSOs);
- Energy Regulators;
- Policy Makers;
- Aggregators;
- ICT, IoT providers;
- Market operators;
- Academia;
- Consumers (Industry, Prosumers and energy communities, EU Citizens);
- Power Producers; and
- Energy Suppliers.

In order to ensure the broadest reach in each of the audience groups mentioned above, and to potentially add new audience groups, some of the ways the project will further identify audiences and create a “user persona” include:

- Customer surveys;
- Research similar projects and topics;
- Collection of demographic data from OneNet’s website analytics; and

- Analysis of newsletter subscribers and social media followers.

These activities will aim at creating a comprehensive overview of all stakeholders to be engaged in OneNet. Based on the expanded list of stakeholders, the communication strategy will be refined in M18, integrating each segment of the reviewed target audiences

2 Dissemination and communications activities

Disseminating and communicating the results and activities of OneNet is fundamental to this large-scale project. In order to ensure diverse and engaging messages, in particular to a variety of external audiences, OneNet has adopted a series of dissemination and communication tools to maximize impact across the board. Importantly, OneNet begins by clarifying its key message to be shared. Thereafter, these messages are translated into the most appropriate format for the channel through which it is being promoted on so that the receiving audience quickly understands the project's goal and results.

2.1 Key communication goals and actions

The project is directing its communication efforts towards achieving the following goals:

- Promote the activities and the results of the project;
- Identify, reach, and engage with stakeholders;
- Drive and support innovation in the grid services market;
- Make the produced knowledge more accessible, inclusive, and actionable;
- Facilitate interaction and feedback/input on our work;
- Improve press & media relations for a marketable result.

Where possible, all resources will be available in open access.

2.2 Communication channels and planning

In the external communications flow, the scope of the project translates the key messages that are disseminated through the different channels:

- OneNet aims at removing the entry barriers to the flex market and ensuring seamless coordination between grid and market operation;
- OneNet aims to create unique synergies between all players at EU and national level; and
- OneNet is more than a project: it's also a platform of cooperation.

Communications channels are medium (both digital and analog) through which our key messages are disseminated to the stakeholders.

- Website: <https://onenet-project.eu/>;
- Newsletter;
- GRIFOn;
- Social media;

- OneNet Twitter;
- OneNet LinkedIn;
- Public relations (i.e. press);
- Partners' websites; and
- Webinars / LIVE and Online Events.

The scheduling of communication activities follows the timing of all of the project's deliverables:

- New publications;
- Milestones;
- Events;
- News from the project network;
- Consultations; and
- GRIFOn activities.

Regular statistics on the impact of the website and social media are gathered and analysed by the WP13 leaders, helping the project coordinator and partners to revise and improve the communication strategy.

WP13 facilitates and supports the participation of the project representatives in main events in the field by doing preliminary research to find the best forums to disseminate the project and network; creating dedicated promo material; doing live coverage of the events on the website and social media; actively engaging with journalists and event organisers and launching partnerships to maximise outreach.

2.3 Corporate identity

As part of task 13.1. General communication and dissemination activities, EUI as WP13 leader, together with the other project partners, defined the project corporate identity and produced the first presentation materials. The project logo was selected by the consortium during the first general assembly in October 2020 from a selection of proposals developed by the EUI. The logo aims at bringing the message of the project together in a simple design that can be easily presented through a number of different mediums.

The outputs of this task were the following:

- Project logo;
- Corporate identity and guidelines;
- Project brochure;
- Project templates (Word and Power Point)
- Virtual backgrounds and other digital graphics

2.4 Making project results available to an external audience

One of the main responsibilities of the WP13 is to make the OneNet project’s results available and visible to a wider audience, which also includes making deliverables available on the website. To date, seven deliverables were published in open access on the website and promoted on LinkedIn and Twitter.

- [D2.1 Review on markets and platforms in related activities](#)
- [D2.2 A set of standardized products for system services in the TSODSO- consumer value chain](#)
- [D3.1 Overview of market designs for the procurement of grid services by DSOs and TSOs](#)
- [D13.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)
- [D13.2 Website with private area](#)
- [D13.3 Project brochure, other project presentation materials and social media](#)
- [D14.1 Data Management Plan](#)

Title	Clicks/Downloads
D2.1 Review on markets and platforms in related activities	10
D2.2 A set of standardized products for system services in the....	15
D3.1 Overview of market designs for the procurement of....	14
D13.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan	5
D13.2 Website with private area	1
D13.3 Project brochure, other project presentation materials	2
D14.1 Data Management Plan	1

Table 2.1 Number of downloads of OneNet deliverables as of 28 September 2021

2.5 Event promotion and support

The following events have been promoted on social media/website/newsletter. WP13 supported the project partners in the communications activities and format, ensuring that the contribution of OneNet would get high exposure.

- **Bridge Horizon2020 General Assembly** (2-4 March 2021, Online event, <https://bit.ly/3BID0fa>)

OneNet partner Fraunhofer participated in the Morning Plenary Session 5: New BRDIGE Projects – Part 3 to present OneNet to the BRIDGE Community. Furthermore, OneNet partner European Dynamics presented OneNet’s project vision in the Parallel Session 2.2: DATA MANAGEMENT WG 2/2.

- **SynErgie-Workshop on Electricity Market Design** (29 June 2021, Online workshop, <https://bit.ly/3h9UVn9>)

The workshop focused on the topic of “Designing Markets for Large Shares of Renewables.” OneNet partner Comillas held a presentation on “Electricity Network Tariffs in a Context of Decarbonization, Digitalization, and Decentralization & OneNet Market Designs for the Procurement of Grid Services by DSOs and TSOs”.

- **2021 IEEE International Forum on Smart Grids for Smart Cities** (17-23 March 2021, Virtual Forum <https://ieeesg4sc.org/>)

OneNet contributions to the IEEE Forum were twofold. Firstly, OneNet partner RWTH organised and held a tutorial on Use Case Analysis and Validation for Smart Grids: Overview of Methods and Tools, together with external partners. Secondly, OneNet operated a project booth in the Projects Zone of the conference to showcase the project and connect with other researchers that are present in the forum.

- **Internal workshop series on use case development based on IEC 62559-2** (21-22 January 2021, internal online workshop)

OneNet Project partner ELES organised a workshop on the development of use cases based on IEC 62559-2.

2.6 Impact of the activities on the website

Below we analyse the data derived from monitoring the website performance, considering some specific metrics and key performance indicators.

2.6.1 Report of page views

The website is online from February 2021. Below is the report of page views until the 31st of August 2021. To date, the homepage is the most visited page, followed by the partners section and the project page.

	Views	Users	New users	View per User
1 Homepage - OneNet Project	2,591	851	74	3.04
2 Partners - OneNet Project	610	347	54	1.76
3 The Project - OneNet Project	591	310	54	1.91
4 Project Brief - OneNet Project	534	246	25	2.17
5 Five things to know about the OneNet Project One Network for Europe	426	277	13	1.54
6 Public Deliverables - OneNet Project	361	207	29	1.74
7 News and Events - OneNet Project	314	166	8	1.89
8 GRIFOn - OneNet Project	310	173	24	1.79
9 Structure - OneNet Project	310	185	16	1.68
10 Demos - OneNet Project	299	155	5	1.93

11 Where are we going? Six months of OneNet Project	147	93	18	1.58
12 Scientific Publications - OneNet Project	140	95	2	1.47
13 Launching OneNet Project: One Network for Europe	108	66	12	1.64
14 Contact us - OneNet Project	95	27	2	3.52
15 OneNet joins the IEEE Forum Smart Grids for Smart Cities	68	39	4	1.74
16 Consortium - OneNet Project	54	6	1	9
17 Press room - OneNet Project	48	16	1	3
18 Privacy Policy - OneNet Project	43	20	5	2.15
19 Bringing the consumers to the centre of the Energy transition	39	23	12	1.7
20 OneNet Project	37	5	0	7.4
21 OneNet flexibility products and market analysis - another step!	33	23	10	1.43
22 News & Events Archives - OneNet Project	29	2	0	14.5
23 Publications - OneNet Project	29	4	0	7.25
24 OneNet Project -	26	5	4	5.2
25 News Archives - OneNet Project	21	3	0	7

Table 2.2 Page views Report

2.6.2 Audience

The users come from Europe (in particular from: Spain, Germany, Belgium, Greece, Poland and Portugal) and worldwide (mainly US).

Users ▾ by Country

Figure 2.1 Users by country

2.6.3 Traffic acquisition

Most of the visits that arrived on our site come from Google (organic search) or directly (by typing the website URL). Another important source of traffic is LinkedIn.

Figure 2.2 Traffic acquisition: Session source/medium (November 2020 – August 2021)

Figure 2.3 Website Page views (November 2020 – June 2021)

2.7 Impact of the blog series

To attract more traffic and engage with stakeholders, the blog series has been created.

Our partners have contributed to the publication of 6 blog posts:

Blog post title	Author	Date of publication
Launching OneNet: One Network for Europe	Claudia Carella (EUI)	October 15, 2020
Five things to know about OneNet project	Valerie Reif (EUI)	February 15, 2020
OneNet joins the IEEE Forum Smart Grids for Smart Cities	Chiara Canestrini (EUI)	March 15, 2021
Where are we going? Six months of OneNet Project	Antonello Monti (Fraunhofer)	April 22, 2021
Bringing the consumers to the centre of the energy transition	Kirsten Glennung and Juan Marco (E.DSO)	July 29, 2021
Giant steps: OneNet flexibility products and market analysis	Poria Divshali (Enerim)	August 25, 2021

Table 2.3 Overview of blog posts on the OneNet Website

In the future, the series will also host contributions from external authors with the purpose of launching new collaborations and increase the outreach and awareness of the project.

2.8 Impact of social media

2.8.1 Twitter

Since its launch in January 2021, the Twitter channel @OneNetProject reached the following:

- 40 Following
- 117 followers
- 17 tweets

Mar 2021 · 31 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 2,785 impressions

👉 The **#OneNet** website is online! 🇺🇸
Find here 5 things worth knowing about the project:

#EuropeanGreenDeal #energy #electricity #TSO #DSO
onenet-project.eu/five-things-to...

🔗 13 ❤️ 25

[View Tweet activity](#) [View all Tweet activity](#)

Top Follower followed by 1,224 people

CEEP
Central Europe Energy Partners

CEEP_energy
@CEEP_energy

Central Europe Energy Partners, the first association to represent the interests of the energy companies from Central Europe at the EU level

[View profile](#)

Top mention earned 19 engagements

INTERFACE H2020
@InterfaceH · Feb 26

👉 In case you missed the 1st **@InterfaceH** Flexibility Solutions webinar, watch the recorded event anytime!

👉 youtu.be/PFpk0WTidbw @EU_H2020 @Energy4Europe @BRIDGE_H2020 @Coordinet_ @eusysflex @OneNetProject

🔗 6 ❤️ 12

[View Tweet](#)

MAR 2021 SUMMARY

Tweets	Tweet Impressions
3	6,288
Profile visits	Mentions
509	8
New followers	
20	

Top media Tweet earned 1,192 impressions

Check out the **#OneNetProject** booth at the IEEE Smart Grids for Smart Cities. Come and say hello 🙋 the OneNet team is waiting for you! pic.twitter.com/vjaYW5UV6j

🔗 1 🗨️ 2 ❤️ 11

[View Tweet activity](#) [View all Tweet activity](#)

Figure 2.4 Twitter General Summary (March 2021)

Your Tweets earned **8.7K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 2.5 Twitter impressions (March-May 2021)

Your Tweets earned **1.9K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 2.6 Twitter impressions (June-August 2021)

2.8.2 LinkedIn

Since its launch, the LinkedIn page reached the following:

- 119 followers
- 8 LinkedIn posts

Visitor metrics ⓘ Time range: Jul 31, 2020 - Jul 30, 2021 Page: All Pages Metric: Page views ▾

Figure 2.7 LinkedIn page views (August 2020 – July 2021)

Visitor demographics ⓘ Time range: Aug 13, 2021 - Aug 27, 2021 Data for: Job function ▾

Figure 2.8 Visitor demographics (August 2021)

2.9 Impact of press release

The press release about the project was shared 19 times on external websites and social media (as found in the partners internal report which can be found below).

Communication & Dissemination template - OneNet

Type of Action	What	Where	When	Who	Link to web page
Web article	News item	REScoop.eu website	29.01.2021	REScoop.eu	Link
Web article	News item	UBITECH Energy website	29.10.2020	UBITECH Energy	Link
Web article	Blog post	EEIP website	25.11.2020	EEIP	Link
Web article	News item	UBITECH Energy website	15.10.2020	UBITECH Energy	Link
Web article	News item	UBITECH website	01.10.2020	UBITECH Energy	Link
Other	Social media post	UBITECH Energy LinkedIn	11.11.2020	UBITECH Energy	Link

Other	Social media post	REScoop.eu twitter	01.03.2021	REScoop.eu	Link
Other	Social media post	REScoop.eu LinkedIn	01.03.2021	REScoop.eu	Link
Other	Social media post	REScoop.eu Facebook	01.03.2021	REScoop.eu	Link
Newsletter	News item	KIOS eNews	15.02.2021	KIOS Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus	Link
Other	Press release	University of Cyprus website	03.02.2021	University of Cyprus	Link
Other	Social media post	E.DSO Twitter	2/26/2021	E.DSO	Link
Web article	Website projects page	E.DSO Website	10/30/2020	E.DSO	Link
Other	Social media post	AST Twitter	02.03.2021	AST	Link
Other	Social media post	AST LinkedIn	02.03.2021	AST	Link
Web Article	News item	European Dynamics website	03.03.2021	European Dynamics	Link
Other	Conference Participation	BRIDGE HORIZON2020 General Assembly	03.03.2021	Dr.George Bouladakis European Dynamics	Link
Other	Social media post	Post in LinkedIn	22.03.2021	Dimitra Makrygiorgou IPTO	Link
Web article	News item	ENTSO-E website	31.01.2021	ENTSO-E	Link
Newsletter	News item	ENTSO-E Newsletter (Wrap-up)	30.10.2020	ENTSO-E	Link

Table 2.4 Communication & Dissemination input by partners- OneNet

Furthermore, the press release received 115 page views on the Florence School of Regulation website (EUI partner):

<https://fsr.eui.eu/fsr-joins-eu-commission-funded-project-onenet/>

- Page views: 115
- Unique Page Views: 91
- Avg. Time on Page: 00:02:09

3 Stakeholder engagement

Interacting with relevant stakeholders and ensuring the project’s outputs are circulating in relevant sectors is a key element of the OneNet. In order to ensure this is done in the most effective manner, a series of newsletters have been prepared and sent to a growing database of contacts in the field. The newsletters themselves bring together all of the most recent activities of OneNet.

3.1 Impact of Database & Newsletters

A dedicated database was built with the purpose of disseminating the project to the interested audiences, via a periodical newsletter. The newsletter collects and highlights all the most relevant updates from the project and its network; it also keeps our audience informed and connected, by offering quick links to our events, publications and other insights from the field, in a visual and web friendly way.

3.1.1 OneNet Newsletter

A subscription form on the OneNet website, a direct link and a QR code were created to build a dedicated database of stakeholders. These were circulated among the partners, on web and social media and in this way, 25 contacts have been collected, in addition to the contacts coming from the network of partners.

The first OneNet newsletter had the following performance:

- Audience: 25 recipients
- Open rate 58.3%
- Click rate 12.5%

Figure 3.1 Newsletter Performance (25 November 2020)

Top locations by opens

Italy	9	30.0%
USA	7	23.3%
Sweden	4	13.3%
Germany	3	10.0%
Belgium	2	6.7%

Figure 3.2 Top locations by opens (25 November 2020)

3.1.2 Other newsletters

In addition to the project database, several partners joined the dissemination efforts and contributed to increase the awareness of the project and spread its message, relying on their existing network. In this context, the OneNet updates have been included in other newsletters, reaching a wider audience of potentially interested contacts. An impactful example is analysed below:

FSR Energy & Climate Newsletter including OneNet announcements (3 newsletters)

- Audience: 12,000 Recipients

Delivered:

- 25 November 2020
- 23 February 2021
- 6 July 2021

Performance:

- Open rate (average) 28.7%
- Click rate (average) 11.2%

4 OneNet Advisory and Dissemination Board

The OneNet Advisory and Dissemination Board (ADB) assesses the overall OneNet approach, use cases and field trials and their implications for the European energy system. The ADB is asked to regularly provide concrete recommendations for the OneNet project to consider adopting in its continued implementation. ADB meetings also serve as an opportunity to identify changes in the framework and new challenges and opportunities for the proposed OneNet solutions. In addition, the ADB advises in the communication of results to stakeholders and helps opening dissemination paths in preparation for exploitation. Members of the ADB help communicate the project results and insights and thereby ensure European-wide acceptance and usability of the OneNet project outcomes.

The ambition of WP13 was to create an ADB with a more technical orientation. Board meetings would serve to provide feedback on specific points that are critical to the project progress at that point in time.

We looked for members with diverse backgrounds with regards to technical expertise and/or business activities relevant for the project. We strived to create a diverse and balanced board taking into consideration criteria, such as expertise, geography, and gender. In addition, we tried to establish some links with the Advisory Board members from other relevant (previous or ongoing) H2020 projects, specifically INTERRFACE and CoordiNet.

4.1 Summary of the process behind the ADB creation

The call for proposals in the GA resulted in a list of 40 candidates with different background and expertise.

- Categories of candidates based on their expertise: TSO-related (5), DSO-related (6), Regulator (5), Research/Academia (9), Consumer-related (3), Consultancy (1), Energy finance (1), Telcom (1), ICT (3), Technology provider (3), Generation/renewables (2), Power Exchange (1)
- Voting rights for PMT members were agreed upon in the March 2021 PMT.
- Requirements for the voting process:
 - The first goal was not to have more than 2 members from the same category.
The PMT later agreed that an exception can be applied to the category “regulator”, due to the added value that the perspective of regulators from different countries could bring to the project.
 - The second goal was to have a balanced representation in terms of expertise, geography and gender; and to consider customer representation.
- The voting was carried out in the PMT (via e-mail).

- The results were proposed to the General Assembly for approval (via e-mail). Due to the size of the consortium, the GA is considered to approve the proposal if no objection is raised by the 4th of June 2021 at noon.

The final OneNet Advisory and Dissemination Board consists of 10 persons, who fulfil the following criteria (expertise, geography, and gender): DSO-related (1), Regulator (4), Research/Academia (2), Consumer-related (1), ICT (1), Power Exchange (1).

4.2 ADB engagement

The ADB met for the first time at the Second General OneNet Assembly, which took place on Monday, 20th of September. The ADB members were invited to the afternoon Technical Session, in which all Work Package leaders presented the work carried out in the OneNet project during the first project year. ADB members engaged in the Q&A sessions following each presentation and gave valuable feedback on the project's interim results and provided some recommendations for the way forward.

5 Conclusions

This intermediate report reflects a promising first step of the project in terms of dissemination and stakeholder engagement. However, most of the activities and results are yet to come.

5.1 Strategy to increase the visibility and impact of the OneNet project

In the next phase of the project, we will scale our communications efforts according to the following priorities:

- **Quality Over Quantity:** Attract new followers using specific keywords (resulting of a preliminary research and analysis) and topics of interest, following the principle “Quality Over Quantity”.
- **Community Engagement:** Encourage interested people to interact with the project by asking for input/feedback, contributing to events/blog series. Explore new tools and formats for collaborative knowledge sharing.
- **Timing:** Increase the chance of people discovering the project output by choosing times and days when the majority of the project followers are online; planning new releases according to the major events and news in the energy field.
- **Optimisation:** Offer original, unique and high-quality content on the website, and optimise the site to make it appear more often and higher up in search results for the related keywords.
- **Visual appeal:** Include visuals on the web, social media and printed communications. New banners, a video, and informative materials will be produced to support the project activities and refresh the identity of the project across the years.
- **Social Media Presence:** Use hashtags and share content from the project and its network, mentioning the partners. Set social media collaborations, cover relevant events (e.g., live tweeting) and craft compelling content tailored to the different channels/audiences.

5.2 New tasks ahead

In the following months, we will be designing and facilitating the project’s events, starting from the Grifon workshop in November 2021.

An educational project video will be produced with the scope of reaching new and less specialised audiences and convey in a simple and attractive way the main activities of the project and the issues at stake. The video will also support the presentations of the project.

The website and social media will be populated by exciting updates and more effort will be put in building a team of “OneNet ambassadors” to generate more debate around the project on web and social media.

The standardisation activities will be addressed by the WP13 partners during the next phase of the project.

WP13 is responsible for dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities and, therefore it is transversal to the rest of the work packages. For that reason, all work packages have contributed to different aspects of the production of this deliverable.

